

Synthesis of novel extractant and its application in extraction and separation studies of palladium(II) in hydrochloric acid medium

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Abstract : A simple and rapid liquid-liquid extraction of palladium(II) studied involving complexation of palladium(II) with 4-(4-ethoxybenzylideneamino)-5-methyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (EBIMTT). The extraction was fast with short shaking time (30 s). The results obtained showed that the average recovery of palladium(II) from an aqueous solution containing $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of analyte was 99% with a relative standard deviation of 0.95. The method is applicable to the analysis of synthetic mixtures. It is highly selective, simple and rapid.

Keywords : Palladium, EBIMTT, solvent extraction, mineral acid.

Introduction

Liquid-liquid extraction is one of the most efficient methods used to separate, and purify metal ions and organic compounds. Extraction has become a technique used to recover and separate precious metals, including palladium(II). This method is proposed for extraction of microgram amounts of palladium(II) from hydrochloric acid medium using EBIMTT dissolved in chloroform as an extractant.

EBIMTT is a sulphur containing ligand, showed promising effects in the field of analytical chemistry for the separation and estimation of platinum group metals¹, the electronegativity also plays an important role in the stability of the complexes containing sulphur as donor atoms. The transition metals normally tends to form covalent bonds and does not form emulsion at the time of extraction.

The effectiveness of EBIMTT has been evaluated as an extractant for Pd^{II} from variety of palladium bearing materials. The important features of this method are that, it permits selective separation of palladium(II) from other platinum group metals and base metals which are generally associated with it. It is free from interference from a large number of foreign ions, low reagent concentration

is required and time needed for equilibration is very short for EBIMTT, about 30 s. We report here the use of EBIMTT as an excellent extractant for palladium(II) from hydrochloric acid medium.

Fig. 1. Structure of 4-(4-ethoxybenzylideneamino)-5-methyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (EBIMTT).

Results and discussion

The extraction of palladium(II) was carried out from different acid media with 0.1 M EBIMTT in chloroform keeping the aq : org ratio 2.5 : 1. The extraction was quantitative from 1–8 M hydrochloric acid. The extraction was found to be quantitative in very high concentration of nitric acid but was incomplete in sulphuric acid. Hence the use of 1 M hydrochloric acid is used for further studies.

Table 1. Effect of foreign ions on the extractive determination of Pd^{II}

Foreign ion	Added as	Amount tolerated (mg)	Foreign ion	Added as	Amount tolerated (mg)
Mn ^{II}	MnCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	10	Pb ^{II}	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	5
Fe ^{II}	FeSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	15	Hg ^{II}	HgCl ₂	5
Fe ^{III}	FeCl ₃	20	Ni ^{II}	NiCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	5
Bi ^{III}	Bi(NO ₃) ₃ .5H ₂ O	20	Co ^{II}	CoCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	15
Zn ^{II}	ZnCl ₂	5	Sn ^{II}	SnCl ₂	5
Ca ^{II}	CaCl ₂	20	Be ^{II}	BeSO ₄ .4H ₂ O	20
Mo ^{VI}	(NH ₄) ₆ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ .24H ₂ O	5	Ba ^{II}	Ba(NO ₃) ₂	20
Pt ^{II}	PtCl ₂	0.5	Cu ^{II a}	CuCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	5
Au ^{III}	HAuCl ₄ .4H ₂ O	1	Pt ^{IV}	H ₂ PtCl ₆	1
Sb ^{III}	Sb ₂ O ₃	5	Cd ^{II}	CdCl ₂ 1/2H ₂ O	5
Fluoride	NaF	200	Sr ^{II}	Sr(NO ₃) ₂	10
EDTA	EDTA (disodium salt)	100	Oxalate	(COOH) ₂ .2H ₂ O	200
Iodide	KI	100	Acetate	CH ₃ COONa	100
Mg ^{II}	MgCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	20	Bromide	KBr	100

Pd^{II} = 100 µg; aqueous phase = 1 M HCl; Aq/Org = 25 : 10; extractant = 0.1 M EBIMTT in chloroform.

^aMask with 100 mg of EDTA.

Palladium(II) was extracted in the presence of different diverse ions (Table 1). The tolerance limit was set as the amount of foreign ions cause $\pm 2\%$ error in recovery of palladium. The results showed that in the extraction and determination 100 µg ml⁻¹ of the palladium, these ions did not interfere at the level tested. The reproducibility of palladium extraction investigated from six replicate measurements was $99.00 \pm 0.95\%$.

Binary separation of palladium(II) from iron(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II): The method allowed separation and determination of palladium(II) from a binary mixture containing either iron(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II). In a typical experiment, solution containing 100 µg of palladium(II) was taken and known amounts of other metals were added. The separation of palladium(II) from iron(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) was accomplished with 0.1 mol/dm³ EBIMTT in chloroform at 1 mol/dm³ hydrochloric acid. Palladium(II) was estimated spectrophotometrically with pyrimidine-2-thiol. The recovery of palladium(II) and that added ions was 99.5% and results are reported in Table 2.

Analysis of alloys: To ascertain the selectivity of the reagent, the proposed method was successfully used in

Table 2. Analysis of synthetic mixture

Amount of metal ion (µg)	Palladium Found (µg)	Recovery ^a (%)	Relative standard deviation (%)
Pd (100) + Au (500)	99.2	99.8	0.04
Pd (100) + Pt (500)	99.1	99.7	0.06
Pd (100) + Rh (200)	99.1	99.6	0.08
Pd (100) + Pt (500) + Rh (200)	98.7	99.7	0.07
Pd (100) + Au (500) + Rh (200)	99.8	99.9	0.07
Pd (100) + Pt (500) + Au (500)	99.5	99.8	0.05
Pd (100) + Pt (500) + Au (500) + Rh (200)	99.6	99.3	0.07
Pd (100) + Pt (500) + Au (500) + Fe (2000) + Co (2000)	99.2	99.4	0.04
Pd (100) + Pt (500) + Au (500) + Rh (200) + Fe (2000) + Co (2000)	98.8	99.6	0.08

^aAverage of six determinations.

the determination of palladium(II) in alloys. The real samples were not available hence the synthetic mixture was prepared corresponding to the composition of alloy. The results of the analysis are reported in Table 3. The average recovery of palladium(II) was 99.5%.

Analysis of synthetic mixtures: The separation of

Table 3. Binary separation of palladium(II) from iron(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II)

Composition of metal ions (μg)	Recovery Pd ^{II} (%)	Relative standard deviation (%)	Recovery added metal ions ^a (%)	Relative standard deviation (%)
Pd ^{II} , 100; Fe ^{III} , 15000	99.6	0.13	99.5	0.19
Pd ^{II} , 100; Co ^{II} , 10000	99.7	0.07	99.4	0.15
Pd ^{II} , 100; Ni ^{II} , 5000	99.6	0.11	99.5	0.16
Pd ^{II} , 100; Cu ^{II} , 5000	99.8	0.13	99.6	0.25

^aAverage of six determinations.

palladium(II) from the platinum group metals and other metals is very difficult. A solution containing 100 μg of palladium(II) was taken and known amount of other metals were added. Under the optimum extraction conditions of palladium(II), there is a quantitative extraction of Au^{III}, Pt^{IV}, Ru^{III} and Rh^{II}. But the co-extracted metal ions cannot be back-stripped by 1 *M* hydrochloric acid solution. Thus, the reagent (EBIMTT) is made selective towards palladium(II) by taking an advantage of the stripant used.

The proposed method allows the separation and determination of palladium(II) from many metal ions and the results of analysis are shown in the Table 4.

Table 4. Analysis of alloys

Alloy	Composition	Palladium taken (μg)	Palladium found ^a (μg)	Recovery (%)	R.S.D. (%)
Low melting dental alloy	Pd, 25; Au, 10; Co, 22; Ni, 34	170	168.83	99.31	0.07
Stibio palladinite mineral	Pd, 75; Sb, 25	150	148.83	99.22	0.07
Jewellery alloy (Pd-Au alloy)	Pd, 50; Au, 50	100	99.86	99.86	0.11
Pd-Cu alloy	Pd, 60; Cu, 40	120	119.5	99.58	0.10
Pd-Ag alloy	Pd, 60; Ag 40	120	119.66	99.9	0.06

^aAverage of six determinations.

Experimental

Synthesis of 4-(4-ethoxybenzylideneamino)-5-methyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (EBIMTT) (Fig 1) :

The equimolar concentration of 3-ethyl-4-amino-5-

mercapto-1,2,4-triazole² and 0.02 mole of ethoxybenzaldehyde in 50 ml alcohol containing 3 drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 3–4 h. The product obtained was separated and recrystallized from hot ethanol as pale yellow needles (m.p. 171 °C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 2.12 (5H, s, -C₂H₅), 6.8 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, aromatic protons), 7.5 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, aromatic protons), 8.1 (1H, s, -CH), 3.08 (1H, s, -SH); IR (cm⁻¹) : 2885 (CH), 1600 ($\gamma\text{C}=\text{N}$) and 754 ($\gamma\text{C}=\text{S}$); Mass *m/e* : 262.09 (100.0%) (M⁺).

A Jasco V-530 UV-Vis spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cells was used for measurement. pH measurements were carried out with an Elico digital pH meter model LI-120 (± 0.01). A stock solution of palladium(II) was prepared by dissolving 1 g of palladium chloride hydrate in dilute analytical reagent hydrochloric acid (1 *M*) diluted to 100 ml with distilled water and standardized gravimetrically³. A working solution of 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ was prepared by diluting the stock solution with distilled water.

EBIMTT (0.1 *M*) solution was prepared in chloroform⁴. Other standard solutions of different metal ions used to study the effect of foreign ions were prepared by dissolving weighed quantities of respective salts in distilled water or dilute hydrochloric acid. Solutions of anions were prepared by dissolving the respective alkali metal salts in distilled water. All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Double distilled water was invariably used throughout the measurements.

General procedure :

An aqueous solution containing 100 μg palladium(II) and enough hydrochloric acid and water were added to give final concentration of 1 *M* with respect to hydro-

chloric acid in 25 ml. The resulting solution was transferred to 125 ml separating funnel. The aqueous phase was equilibrated once with 10 ml of 0.1 M EBIMTT solutions in chloroform for 30 s. The phase was allowed to separate and the metal from the organic phase was back stripped with two 5 ml portions of 50% ammonia solution. The extract was evaporated to moist dryness. The residue was dissolved in minimum amount of dilute hydrochloric acid to form the solution. Palladium(II) was estimated spectrophotometrically with pyrimidine-2-thiol.

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